

International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research (IJHRIR)

ISSN: 2349 -3593 (Online) ISSN: 2349 -4816 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-2-june-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and subscription

IMPACT OF MANPOWER PLANNING ON EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Ankita Dhamija

Research Scholar, Mahatma Gandhi University, India.

Dr. R.K.Gupta

Mahatma Gandhi University, India

Abstract

This paper is written with the intention of establishing the impact of manpower planning on employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction. An employee satisfaction is considered as a key factor for an organisations success. It is that the top management who recruit their employees who are confident and those who can display pro-social dispositions. There are many dispositional factors such as self -efficacy, corporative orientation etc that have a moderate impact of employee satisfaction on customer satisfaction. Many measures support that employee satisfaction is a factor in employee motivation, employee goal achievement and positive employee morale in the work place. Basically employee satisfaction is a measure of how happy is the workers with their job and with their organisational working environment. In this paper various variables responsible for employee satisfaction will be discussed such as Organization development factors, Job security

factors, Work task factors, Policies of compensation and benefit factor and opportunities which gives satisfaction to employees such as Promotion and career development also has been described .This paper also deals the various ways by which one can improve employee satisfaction whose end result is customer satisfaction by getting advantage of employee satisfaction.

Key Word: *Employee Satisfaction, customer satisfaction, management, Job Security, Environment*

**Corresponding author: * Ankita Dhamija*

Reference this paper as: *Ankita Dhamija & Gupta R.K, (2014). "Impact Of Manpower Planning On Employee Satisfaction And Customer Satisfaction," International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research, Vol.1, Issue 2, May-2014, pp 01-06*

Introduction:

Manpower Planning: Manpower Planning which is also called as Human Resource Planning consists of putting right number of people, right kind of people at the right place, right time, doing the right things for which they are suited for the achievement of goals of the organization. Human Resource Planning has got an important place in the arena of industrialization. Human Resource Planning has to be a systems approach and is carried out in a set procedure. The procedure for effective manpower planning is as follows:

- Analysing the current manpower inventory
- Making future manpower forecasts
- Gap analysis
- Developing employment programmes
- Design training programmes

Importance of Manpower Planning

- **Key to managerial functions-** The four managerial functions, i.e., planning, organizing, directing and controlling are based upon the manpower. Human resources help in the implementation of all these managerial activities. Therefore, staffing becomes a key to all managerial functions.

- **Efficient utilization-** Efficient management of personnel's becomes an important function in the industrialization world of today. Setting of large scale enterprises requires management of large scale manpower. It can be effectively done through staffing function.

- **Motivation-** Staffing function not only includes putting right men on right job, but it also comprises of motivational programmes, i.e., incentive plans to be framed for further participation and employment of employees in a concern. Therefore, all types of incentive plans become an integral part of staffing function.

- **Better human relations-** A concern can stabilize itself if human relations develop and are strong. Human relations become strong

through effective control, clear communication, effective supervision and leadership in a concern. Staffing function also looks after training and development of the work force which leads to co-operation and better human relations.

- **Higher productivity-** Productivity level increases when resources are utilized in best possible manner. Higher productivity is a result of minimum wastage of time, money, efforts and energies. This is possible through the staffing and its related activities (Performance appraisal, training and development, remuneration)

Employee Satisfaction: Employees are called the human capital in any business. To make this human capital productive, it is necessary to make them satisfy so that we can use them effectively and efficiently. Employee satisfaction is defined as whether employees are happy or they are able to fulfil their desires and needs at work environment.

Customer Satisfaction: Customers are the king to any organisation. Customers satisfaction are measured by the degree at which organisations are able to fulfil the needs of the customers.

Objective:

The primary objective

- To know the relationship between the manpower planning with employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction

Secondary Objective

- to know the impact of manpower planning on employee satisfaction
- To Know the impact of manpower planning on customer satisfaction

Research Methodology: This study is based on conceptual based study. The analysis and conclusion is based on secondary data. The study is based on experiences gathered through secondary data

Literature Review

The effects of dissatisfaction that results in an employee's withdrawal from job and company can range from mild to severe. Tardiness, in showing up for work and coming back from breaks, shows a lack of interest by the employee for his or her responsibilities. This may escalate to the employee not showing up to work entirely. Some less obvious signs of withdrawal from the job include: taking care of personal matters while at work, playing games, engaging in non-work related talk, spending time on social networks, and diminishing job performance. These withdrawal behaviors, when evidence of dissatisfaction, may end with an employee leaving the workplace; "then heuristic model posits that thinking of quitting is the most probable outcome of job dissatisfaction" (Koslowsky & Krausz, 2002). Therefore, withdrawal will lead either to the employee voluntarily leaving the organization or being terminated for unprofessional behaviour. Happiness in the workplace leads to much higher levels of productivity. It increases employee morale; therefore employees are more willing to work harder to improve the company and its goals.

According to Branham (2005), "Gallup studies show that businesses with higher employee satisfaction also have:

- 86% higher customer ratings
- 76% more success in lowering turnover
- 70% higher profitability
- 44% higher profitability
- 78% better safety records."

Connection to the company gives staff a better feeling of belonging and worth. Supervisors should set an example by promoting friendly relationships with the staff so the work environment is healthier (Kaye & Jordan-Evans, 1999). They need to learn to listen to the employees when they have a concern or a question about the work that they are doing or the direction that the company is taking. It is imperative that managers show respect for all employees, their opinions, and their work. Managers need to convey a good understanding of the mission and goals that the company is trying to attain so that the staff recognizes what

the organization is working toward. Clarification, of the expectations associated with different positions, assists employees in comprehending their direct relationship with the company and how their work affects that of others. Performance reviews are a good managerial tool because they give administrators an idea of those employees that are contributing to the organization's success and those who need to work harder (Branham, 2005). It also offers employees the ability to gauge their performance. Often, employees will think that they are performing better or worse than their managers perceive their work to be. The performance review presents the perfect time to bring together these different perspectives, to correct negative behavior, and to reward productivity.

Providing employees with the opportunity for growth is also a major contributor to satisfaction. Because performing the same job becomes uninteresting, it is important to challenge employees with work that they can accomplish but stretches their abilities (Timpe, 1986). It is a good opportunity to see the abilities of lower level employees. Giving employees new projects or goals allows them to become creative and skilled in new areas. This broadens their knowledge while they become a more valuable asset to the company. Lateral movement does not change the status of the employee, but helps them learn more about different aspects of the company. Doing another job entirely gives the employee a change of pace and direction. The 35employee may find that they enjoy a different branch of the workforce better than the one previously held.

Impact of Effective Manpower Planning on Employee Satisfaction: Employees are the assets of every organisation. They feel satisfied if their basic working environmental needs are satisfied and are being provided the basic tools and techniques to perform their jobs.

- **Employee Motivation:** An employee of any organisation is feeling motivated if he is working at his interest area profile. And Manpower planning is all about fitting the right person at right job at right time. So the employee is satisfied if he is fitted as per his skill and

organisation is getting better productivity so the human resource department is also feeling good about its effective manpower planning.

- **Employee Loyalty:** If the employee is satisfied he will be perform effectively, creates goodwill of the organisation and will be loyal towards the organisation.
- **Performance Improvement:** An employee in the organisation will try to improve his performance only if he is getting all the benefits like good working environment, compensation benefits which is again a part of effective manpower planning.
- **Achievement of Career Goals:** Career planning is a part of manpower planning. An employee will be sent to right job at right time when he is clear about his career goals. His career planning will be done accordingly. And if an employee is aware of the fact that organisation is concern about his career, then he will be satisfied and perform better.
- **Less Skill Gap:** In effective manpower planning i.e fitting the right person at right place at right time, there will be less gap between the job requirement skills and employees skill which leads to employee satisfaction.
- **Self confident:** Effective manpower planning make the employee to perform better and will result in self confident in that job which leads to employee satisfaction.
- **Recognition by top Management:** An employee effective performance which is a result of effective manpower planning use to be recognition by top management. He will feel empowered and feel satisfy.
- **Innovation:** The employees who are fit at the right job, they feel satisfied. The satisfied minds brings new innovation in the organisation, creation of new ideas,

products and services which again boost up their moral.

- **Positive working Conditions:** The working environment in which we are working need to be positive as positive environment leads to effective results, employee satisfaction. Environment is positive because employees are placed at their exact positions ,there is no role conflict which shows effective manpower planning.
- **Self Development:** The employees who are satisfied with their existing situation get time for self development which get the better opportunities to Human resource department to do effective manpower planning.
- **Lower Attrition Rate:** Satisfied employees who are fit and comfortable in their job usually avoid changing their job on frequent basis which shows low attrition rate.
- **Lower Level of Stress:** satisfied employees with effective manpower planning leads to lower level of stress and make the job of Human resource department job easier. They need not to go for stress management trainings.
- **Lower Cost:** There is less cost incurred on training of satisfied employees and as there will low attrition rate in satisfied employees so there will be less recruitment and selection cost.

Impact of Effective Manpower Planning on Customer Satisfaction: Customer is the king to every organisation. If we fit the right person at right job at right time then the customers use to get the following benefits

- **Quality Products:** The quality products are being manufactured by the employees whose skills support the creation and innovation in product. and these quality products helps directly in satisfying the customers.

- **Less Response time:** There are employees who are pro active in responding the customers because are hired as per effective manpower planning for this particular job. Their response time is minimum which make the customers satisfy.
- **Customer retention:** Customers are retaining when the employees make their customers satisfy with different queries that are being asked by customers because are hired as per effective manpower planning for this particular job.
- **Effective After sale services:** Sales executives are there to help the customers to handle their problems related to the products on call as effective manpower planning results in better suited person for this type of job.
- **Brand Loyalty:** The satisfy customers results in brand loyalty. This can only be done with the efforts of the employees and human resource department. As the human resource department is working indirectly to satisfy customers. As HR Department hire right person at right job at right time so that employees give best of their services to their customers.
- **Price Fairness:** To make customer satisfy , organisation need to sell its product at fair price. This can only be done with the help of Human resource department. If HR department provide the right person at the time of costing of product so that organisation may charge the genuine and reasonable price for the products and services that they sell.
- **Innovative Products:** Customers get satisfaction if their needs get satisfied. With the change in time the demand for latest technology is also increasing. So to satisfy our customers , HR department is required to hire employees with latest technology as part of effective manpower planning who can innovate new ideas in manufacturing of goods and services to satisfy customers.

A few basic rules about customer service:

- Honesty is the Best Policy.
- Integrity – Be honest and own up to your mistakes.
- Break Glass in Case of Fire. Response Time –
- Keeping it Real. Set a Realistic Expectation
- R-E-S-P-E-C-T.

Relationship between Employee Satisfactions with Customer Satisfaction in Lieu of Effective Manpower Planning:

Creating a balance between employee satisfaction and customers satisfaction is very critical phase for any particular organisation. If the employees are not satisfied with the organisation then their performance level reduces and output contributed by them comes down to a great extent and so the products are not supplied to the customers at the right time. The following are the results of relationship between the employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction in lieu of effective manpower planning.

- **Communication:** The communication between the employees and customers is very important. Lack in communication results in poor performance of employees, losing customers, reputation of organisation might be ruined. So Human resource Department prefer to do effective manpower planning of those employees who are in touch with customers directly.
- **Accountability and Authority:** The employees are accountable and have authority to take decisions. Lacking and delay in decision making might result in delay to delivery of goods on time to customers. So to satisfy our customers, it is necessary to satisfy our employees by making them accountable for different task and empower them by giving authority. This can be done effectively by better manpower planning.

- **Training/Knowledge/Growth:** Employees feel satisfy if human resource department do effective manpower planning by providing them training, enhancing their knowledge and provide them chance to grow. These add on learning in employees bring innovation in products and services which leads to customer satisfaction.
- **Action plan:** Effective manpower planning leads to fitting the right person at right job which make the employees satisfy and this type of employee don't leave the organisations easily. And this type of employees provide better action plan with the help of their past experience and end in on time customer service and make the customers satisfy.
- **Performance indicators:** The employees are evaluated on the basis of performance indicators which are directly related to customer satisfaction as employees performance indicators helps in better and effective manpower planning for next time for the same employee.
- **Trust and respect:** Employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction both is dependent on each other with trust and respect. Customers should trust on employees of the organisation that they will provide quality goods with all best services. Employees should trust customers on their new innovation and their performance which again is a part of effective manpower planning.
- **Customer survey:** The customers who are satisfy with goods and services provide positive feedback of the goods and services that they have used. The Customer survey initiative is taken by only those employees who are satisfy with their performance. Again the better performance is the result of effective manpower planning.

Conclusion: It is necessary to have effective manpower planning which results in employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction as we have discussed the impact of manpower

planning on employee satisfaction as well as on the customer satisfaction. In reality these three concepts are so closely inter related to each other that studying each and every aspect of these concept is not so easy. But the researcher has tried to bring into the notice the few aspects related to all these concepts.

References:

<http://managementhelp.org/customers/service.htm>